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2012

NATIONAL EVOLUTIONARY SYNTHESIS CENTER
ANNUAL REPORT APPENDICES

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DISCIPLINES OF SUPPORTED PROJECTS IN YEAR 8

Center Project

Meeting

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APPENDIX A

DISCIPLINES OF SUPPORTED PROJECTS IN YEAR 8

	CENTER PROJECT	MEETING			VISITING FELLOW					TOTAL
		OTHER	CATALYSIS MEETING	WORKING GROUP	GRADUATE FELLOW	JOURNALIST IN RESIDENCE	LONG-TERM SABBATICAL	POSTDOCTORAL FELLOW	SHORT-TERM VISITOR	
APPLIED EVOLUTION	0	0	2	3	0	1	0	2	0	8
BEHAVIOR OR NEUROBIOLOGY	0	0	0	2	0	0	1	4	2	9
BIODIVERSITY	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	4
COMPARATIVE BIOLOGY	2	0	3	3	1	0	1	3	7	20
DEVELOPMENT	0	0	2	0	1	0	0	1	1	5
EDUCATION	0	0	3	3	1	0	0	0	2	9
EVOLUTIONARY ECOLOGY OR POPULATION BIOLOGY	1	1	4	9	2	0	4	10	5	36
GENOMICS OR PROTEOMICS	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	3	1	8
MOLECULAR EVOLUTION	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	7	3	13
PALEONTOLOGY	0	0	0	4	2	0	1	4	3	14
PHYLOGEOGRAPHY OR SPECIATION	0	0	2	1	2	0	0	2	3	20
PHYSIOLOGY OR FUNCTIONAL MORPHOLOGY	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	4
POPULATION OR EVOLUTIONARY GENETICS	0	0	5	3	0	0	2	3	2	15
SYSTEMATICS OR PHYLOGENETICS	1	0	1	6	3	1	1	5	6	24
OTHER	1	2	6	6	0	1	1	3	1	21
CLIMATE CHANGE	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
EVOLUTIONARY MEDICINE	0	0	1	3	0	1	1	0	1	7
HUMAN EVOLUTION	0	1	3	1	0	0	0	0	1	6
ORIGINS OF LIFE	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
SYNTHETIC BIOLOGY	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	3

APPENDIX B

DEMOGRAPHICS OF PI'S AND CO-PI'S IN YEAR 8

APPX B1: GENDER OF PROJECT PI'S AND CO-PI'S IN YEAR 8

CATEGORY	CATALYSIS MEETING	GRADUATE FELLOW	JOURNALIST IN RESIDENCE	LONG-TERM SABBATICAL	POSTDOCTORAL FELLOW	SHORT-TERM VISITOR	TRIANGLE SCHOLAR	WORKING GROUP	GRAND TOTAL
FEMALE	9	3	0	2	8	8	0	16	46
MALE	28	2	1	3	10	12	1	31	88
OTHERS	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
TOTAL	37	5	2	5	18	20	1	47	135

APPX B2: ETHNICITY OF PROJECT PI'S AND CO-PI'S IN YEAR 8

CATEGORY	CATALYSIS MEETING	GRADUATE FELLOW	JOURNALIST IN RESIDENCE	LONG-TERM SABBATICAL	POSTDOCTORAL FELLOW	SHORT-TERM VISITOR	TRIANGLE SCHOLAR	WORKING GROUP	GRAND TOTAL
HISPANIC OR LATINO	1	0	0	1	3	1	0	4	10
NOT HISPANIC OR LATINO	35	5	1	4	14	17	0	41	117
DO NOT WISH TO PROVIDE	1	0	0	0	1	2	1	2	7
NO ANSWER	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
TOTAL	37	5	2	5	18	20	1	47	135

APPX B3: RACE OF PROJECT PI'S AND CO-PI'S IN YEAR 8

CATEGORY	CATALYSIS MEETING	GRADUATE FELLOW	JOURNALIST IN RESIDENCE	LONG-TERM SABBATICAL	POSTDOCTORAL FELLOW	SHORT-TERM VISITOR	TRIANGLE SCHOLAR	WORKING GROUP	GRAND TOTAL
ASIAN	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	3
BLACK OR AFRICAN	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
HISPANIC OR LATINO	0	0	0	1	2	1	0	4	8
WHITE	34	5	1	4	13	16	1	40	114
DO NOT WISH TO PROVIDE	1	0	0	0	2	1	0	3	7
NO ANSWER	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
TOTAL	37	5	2	5	18	20	1	47	135

APPX B4: NATIONALITY OF PROJECT PI'S AND CO-PI'S IN YEAR 8

CATEGORY	CATALYSIS MEETING	GRADUATE FELLOW	JOURNALIST IN RESIDENCE	LONG-TERM SABBATICAL	POSTDOCTORAL FELLOW	SHORT-TERM VISITOR	TRIANGLE SCHOLAR	WORKING GROUP	GRAND TOTAL
US CITIZEN	31	4	1	5	13	11	1	38	104
PERMANENT RESIDENT	2	0	0	0	2	0	0	3	7
NON-US CITIZEN	3	1	0	0	3	9	0	6	22
DO NOT WISH TO PROVIDE	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
NO ANSWER	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
TOTAL	37	5	2	5	18	20	1	47	135

APPENDIX C

DEMOGRAPHICS OF PARTICIPANTS IN NESCENT ACTIVITIES IN YEAR 8

APPX C1: GENDER OF PARTICIPANTS IN YEAR 8

CATEGORY	CATALYSIS MEETING	COURSE	WORKING GROUP	GRAND TOTAL
FEMALE	72	7	139	218
MALE	123	32	210	365
DO NOT WISH TO PROVIDE	3	0	7	10
NO ANSWER	15	3	21	39
TOTAL	213	42	377	632

APPX C2: ETHNICITY OF PARTICIPANTS IN YEAR 8

CATEGORY	CATALYSIS MEETING	COURSE	WORKING GROUP	GRAND TOTAL
HISPANIC OR LATINO	35	9	58	102
NOT HISPANIC OR LATINO	124	22	245	391
DO NOT WISH TO PROVIDE	39	6	51	96
NO ANSWER	15	5	23	43
TOTAL	213	42	377	632

APPX C3: RACE OF PARTICIPANTS IN YEAR 8

CATEGORY	CATALYSIS MEETING	COURSE	WORKING GROUP	GRAND TOTAL
BLACK OR AFRICAN AMERICAN	13	0	0	13
HISPANIC OR LATINO	0	0	32	32
WHITE	192	23	307	522
DO NOT WISH TO PROVIDE	8	19	38	65
TOTAL	213	42	377	632

APPX C3: NATIONALITY OF PARTICIPANTS IN YEAR 8

CATEGORY	CATALYSIS MEETING	COURSE	WORKING GROUP	GRAND TOTAL
US CITIZEN	88	16	176	280
PERMANENT RESIDENT	27	2	48	77
NON-US CITIZEN	79	19	121	219
DO NOT WISH TO PROVIDE	4	0	10	14
NO ANSWER	15	5	22	42
TOTAL	213	42	377	632

APPENDIX D

COUNTRIES OF UNIQUE PARTICIPANTS' INSTITUTION

PARTICIPANTS BY COUNTRY

■ 386 TO 386 (1)	■ 14 TO 39 (2)	■ 4 TO 8 (6)	■ 2 TO 3 (6)
■ 39 TO 386 (1)	■ 8 TO 14 (2)	■ 3 TO 4 (4)	■ 1 TO 2 (16)

AUSTRALIA	18	GERMANY	5	NORWAY	2
AUSTRIA	2	GREECE	1	PHILIPPINES	3
BELGIUM	2	GUADELOUPE	1	QATAR	1
BRAZIL	4	HUNGARY	1	SOUTH AFRICA	1
CANADA	21	INDIA	2	SOUTH KOREA	1
CHINA	1	INDONESIA	2	SPAIN	3
CZECH REPUBLIC	1	IRELAND	1	SWEDEN	4
DENMARK	2	ISRAEL	1	SWITZERLAND	5
ECUADOR	1	ITALY	6	TAIWAN, ROC	1
EGYPT	1	JAPAN	6	THE NETHERLANDS	2
FINLAND	3	MEXICO	2	UNITED KINGDOM	44
FRANCE	8	NETHERLANDS	8	UNITED STATES	474
FRENCH POLYNESIA	1	NEW ZEALAND	6	GRAND TOTAL	663

APPENDIX E

U.S. STATES OF UNIQUE PARTICIPANTS' INSTITUTION

ALASKA	2	KANSAS	6	OHIO	9
ALABAMA	3	KENTUCKY	3	OKLAHOMA	2
ARKANSAS	3	LOUISIANA	3	OREGON	11
ARIZONA	13	MASSACHUSETTS	22	PENNSYLVANIA	14
CALIFORNIA	84	MARYLAND	11	RHODE ISLAND	11
COLORADO	13	MAINE	1	SOUTH CAROLINA	4
CONNECTICUT	20	MICHIGAN	11	SOUTH DAKOTA	3
DC	8	MINNESOTA	5	TENNESSEE	15
DELAWARE	1	MISSOURI	8	TEXAS	14
FLORIDA	16	MONTANA	2	UTAH	2
GEORGIA	14	NORTH CAROLINA	127	VIRGINIA	13
HAWAII	4	NEBRASKA	7	WASHINGTON	13
IOWA	2	NEW HAMPSHIRE	5	WISCONSIN	8
IDAHO	6	NEW JERSEY	8	WYOMING	3
ILLINOIS	14	NEW MEXICO	4		
INDIANA	16	NEW YORK	27	TOTAL	579

PARTICIPANTS BY STATE

APPENDIX F

DETAILED LIST OF ACTIVITIES AND PARTICIPANTS IN YEAR 7

CATALYSIS MEETINGS

AN INTEGRATIVE UNDERSTANDING OF THE EVOLUTION OF GENOMIC IMPRINTING

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=264

DATES: 12/2/2011 - 12/6/2011

PI

Jason Wolf

COPI

Francisco Ubeda

Hamish Spencer

PARTICIPANTS

Greg Hunt

David Queller

Rebecca Oakey

Robert Feil

James Curley

Marilyn Renfree

Jon Wilkins

Bernard Crespi

Russell Bonduriansky

Jonathan Mill

Jason Wolf

Francisco Ubeda

Gavin Kelsey

Jeremy Van Cleve

Randy Jirtle

Mike Wade

Louis Lefebvre

Manus Patten

Ueli Grossniklaus

Deborah Bourc'his

Anne Ferguson-Smith

Laura Ross

Yaniv Brandvain

Benjamin Normark

Andrew Clark

Hamish Spencer

Marisa Bartolomei

INSTITUTION

University of Bath

University of Tennessee-Knoxville

University of Otago (New Zealand)

Purdue Univ

Washington University St. Louis

King's College London

CNRS Institute of Molecular Genetics

Columbia University

The University of Melbourne (AUSTRALIA)

Santa Fe Institute

Simon Fraser University

University of New South Wales

Institute of Psychiatry, King's College London

University of Bath

University of Tennessee-Knoxville

Babraham Institute

Santa Fe Institute (Santa Fe, NM)

Duke University

Indiana University

University of British Columbia

Georgetown University

University of Zurich

Institut Curie Paris

University of Cambridge

Oxford University

UC Davis

U. Mass. Amherst

Cornell University

University of Otago

University of Pennsylvania School of Medicine

CATALYSIS MEETINGS, CONTINUED

TRANSITIONS BETWEEN MUTUALISM & PARASITISM: INTEGRATING THEORY & EMPIRICISM

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=313

DATES: 2/28/2012 - 3/2/2012

PI

Michele Dudash

INSTITUTION

University of Maryland-College Park (College Park,MD)

COPI

Nat Holland

University of Houston

PARTICIPANTS

Tom Little

University of Edinburgh

Susan Kephart

Wilamette University

Stefan Doetterl

University of Bayreuth

Arjen Biere

Netherlands Inst Ecol

Richard Reynolds

University of Alabama at Birmingham

David Wagner

University of Connecticut

Anna-Liisa Laine

University of Helsinki

Bengt Oxelman

University of Gothenburg

Christina M Caruso

University of Guelph

Liz Zimmer

Smithsonian Institution

Jana Jicinska

National Museum of Natural History

Janet Steven

Sweet Briar College

Lynda Delph

Indiana University

Michael Hood

Amherst College

Charles Fenster

University of Maryland

Doug Taylor

University of Virginia

Juannan Zhou

University of Maryland

Nat Holland

University of Houston

Michele Dudash

University of Maryland-College Park (College Park,MD)

Mike Wade

Indiana University

THE MOLECULAR ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION OF THE INDO-PACIFIC: A COLLABORATIVE RESEARCH NETWORK

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=290

DATES: 3/5/2012 - 3/8/2012

PI

Eric Crandall

INSTITUTION

University of California-Santa Cruz

COPI

Cynthia Riginos

University of Queensland

PARTICIPANTS

Aditya R. Kartadikaria

Tokyo Institute of Technology

Satoshi Mitarai

Okinawa Institute of Science and Technology

Nina Yasuda

university of Miyazaki

Kent Carpenter

Old Dominion University

Steve Palumbi

Stanford University

Chris Bird

University of Hawaii

Sophie von der Heyden

Stellenbosch University

CATALYSIS MEETINGS, CONTINUED

Kartik Shanker	Indian Institute of Sciences
Rachel Ravago-Gotanco	University of the Philippines, Diliman
Mark Erdmann	Conservation International
Suzanne Williams	Natural History Museum of the UK
Johnathan Kool	Geoscience Australia
Eric Trembl	University of Queensland
Hamid Toha	Universitas Negeri Papua
Lynne Van Herwerden	James Cook University
Harilaos Lessios	Smithsonian Tropical Research Institute
Elizabeth J Sbrocco	Boston University
Marie-Antonette Juinio-Menez	University of the Philippines
Cecile Fauvelot	Institut de Recherche pour le Developpement
Maria Celia Malay	De La Salle University - Manila
Maria Beger	University of Queensland
Brian Bowen	University of Hawaii
Giacomo Bernardi	University of California - Santa Cruz
Serge Planes	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
Kim Selkoe	University of California Santa Barbara
Chris Meyer	Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History
Michael Hickerson	Queens College and the CUNY Graduate Center
Rob Toonen	University of Hawaii
Paul Barber	University of California - Los Angeles
Gustav Paulay	University of Florida
Eric Crandall	University of California-Santa Cruz
Cynthia Riginos	University of Queensland
Amanda Ackiss	Old Dominion University
Peter J Unmack	NESCent
Helen Fox	World Wildlife Fund
Luiz Rocha	California Academy of Sciences

EVOLUTION OF HUMAN TEETH AND JAWS: IMPLICATIONS FOR DENTISTRY AND ORTHODONTICS

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=309

DATES: 3/28/2012 - 3/30/2012

PI

Peter Ungar

COPI

John Sorrentino

Jerome Rose

PARTICIPANTS

Kevin Boyd

Jerome Rose

Subhash Walimbe

Andrea Taylor

INSTITUTION

University of Arkansas

John A. Sorrentino, DMD, FAGD

University of Arkansas Main Campus (Fayetteville,AR)

Private practice/Chicago Children's Memorial Hospital

University of Arkansas Main Campus (Fayetteville,AR)

University of Pune

Duke University

CATALYSIS MEETINGS, CONTINUED

Christine E Wall	Duke University
Debbie Guatelli-Steinberg	The Ohio State University
Mark Teaford	Highpoint University
Peter W Lucas	The George Washington University
David Daegling	University of Florida
Bill Hylander	Duke University
Simon Hillson	University College London
Alison Elgart	Florida Gulf Coast University)
Kristin Krueger	Wright State University
Deborah Redford Badwal	University of Connecticut
Ann Gibbons	Science Magazine
Roger Badwal	Private practice
Robert Coruccini	Southern Illinois University
Louise Humphrey	The Natural History Museum - London
Andrea Cucina	Universidad Autónoma de Yucatan
Christopher Dean	University College London
John Sorrentino	John A. Sorrentino, DMD, FAGD
Peter Ungar	University of Arkansas
Richard Kay	Duke University
Wendy Dirks	Newcastle University

TRACKING THE BIOTIC RESPONSE TO GLOBAL CLIMATE CHANGE THROUGH GENOMIC ANALYSIS

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=311

DATES: 4/27/2012 - 4/29/2012

PI

Alan Bergland

INSTITUTION

Stanford University (,CA)

COPI

Paul Schmidt

Univ. of Pennsylvania

Dmitri Petrov

Stanford University

PARTICIPANTS

Kimberley Hughes

Florida State University

Chau-Ti Ting

National Taiwan University

John Colbourne

Indiana University

Subhash Rajpurohit

University of Georgia

Jean Philippe Lessard

University of Copenhagen

Julien Ayroles

Harvard University

Kelly Dyer

University of Georgia

Josefa Gonzalez

Institute of Evolutionary Biology

Brian Lazzaro

Cornell University

Regan Early

Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales

Thomas Flatt

Institute for Population Genetics, Vetmeduni Vienna

David Kidd

Kingston University London

Maaria Kankare

University of Jyvaskyla

Brian Helmuth

University of South Carolina

CATALYSIS MEETINGS, CONTINUED

Dmitri Petrov	Stanford University
James Fry	University of Rochester
Hannah Burrack	North Carolina State University
Paul Schmidt	Univ. of Pennsylvania
Maaïke de Jong	University of Helsinki
Nadia Singh	North Carolina State University
John Pool	University of Wisconsin-Madison
Fabian Staubach	Stanford University
Stephen Porder	Brown University
Siu Fai Lee	University of Melbourne
Alan Bergland	Stanford University (,CA)
Alisa Sedghifar	University of California, Davis

PATHS TO CEPHALOPOD GENOMICS- STRATEGIES, CHOICES, ORGANIZATION

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=312

DATES: 5/24/2012 - 5/27/2012

PI

Clifton Ragsdale

INSTITUTION

University of Chicago (Chicago,IL)

COPI

Leonid Moroz

Whitney Laboratory for Marine Bioscience, Univ. Florida

Laure Bonnaud

University Paris Diderot-Paris 7

PARTICIPANTS

Brian Dilkes

Purdue University

Sarah Zylinski

Duke Univeristy

David Glanzman

University of California-Los Angeles

Carlo Di Cristo

University of Sannio

Marie-Therese

Noedl Italian Institute of Technology

Kristen Koenig

University of Texas-Austin

Patrick Minx

The Genome Institute-Washington University

Leonid Moroz

Whitney Laboratory for Marine Bioscience, Univ. Florida

Clifton Ragsdale

University of Chicago (Chicago,IL)

Laure Bonnaud

University Paris Diderot-Paris 7

Eric Edsinger-Gonzales

University of California-Berkeley

Bob Freeman

Harvard Medical School

Wendy Crookes

Wright-Patterson AFB-Ohio

Carlos Canchaya

University of Vigo

Rute da Fonseca

Natural History Museum of Denmark

C. Titus Brown

Michigan State University

Judit Pungor

Stanford University

Caroline Albertin

University of Chicago

Joshua Rosenthal

University of Puerto Rico-Medical Sciences Campus

Shuichi Shigeno

Japan Agency for Marine-Earth Science & Technology

Mark Martindale

Kewalo Marine Lab/Univ. Hawaii

Tim Wollesen

University of Vienna

CATALYSIS MEETINGS, CONTINUED

Erich Schwarz	Cornell University
Guojie Zhang	BGI-Shenzhen
Jan Strugnell	La Trobe University
Annie Lindgren	Portland State University
Spencer Nyholm	University of Connecticut
Roger Hanlon	Marine Biological Laboratory & Brown University
Atsushi Ogura	Ochanomizu University

USING GENETICS AND GENEALOGY TO TEACH EVOLUTION AND HUMAN DIVERSITY

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=321

DATES: 6/21/2012 - 6/23/2012

PI

Nina G Jablonski

INSTITUTION

NESCent

COPI

Henry Gates

Harvard University

Mark Shriver

Pennsylvania State University

PARTICIPANTS

Robin E Bulleri

Carrboro High School

Beaux Berkeley

James Madison University (Harrisonburg,VA)

Michael Campbell

University of Pennsylvania School of Medicine

Rick Kittles

University of Illinois at Chicago

Jose Fernandez

University of Alabama Birmingham

Nina G Jablonski

Pennsylvania State University

Monique Scott

American Museum of Natural History

Misha Angrist

Duke University

Henry Gates,

Harvard University

Heather Zimmerman

Pennsylvania State University

Mark Shriver

Pennsylvania State University

Bert Ely

University of South Carolina

Aditi Pai

Spelman College

Jennifer Wagner

University of Pennsylvania

Wallace Sharif

Morehouse College

Leah Walczak

New England Historic Genealogical Society

David Eltis

Emory University

Eric Plutzer

Pennsylvania State University

Abby Wolf

Harvard University

Blaine Bettinger Bond

Schoeneck & King, PLLC

Rinaldo Pereira

Universidade Catolica de Brasilia

Joseph L Graves Jr

North Carolina A & T State University

Samuel Richards

Pennsylvania State University

Jennifer Eberhardt

Stanford University

Catherine Bliss

Brown University

CATALYSIS MEETINGS, CONTINUED

THE ROLE OF MOUNTAINS, CLIMATE, AND LANDSCAPE IN GENERATING AMAZON/ANDEAN BIODIVERSITY

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=339

DATES: 11/1/2012 - 11/3/2012

PI

Paul Baker

INSTITUTION

Duke University

COPI

Sherilyn Fritz

University of Nebraska-Lincoln

Christopher Dick

University of Michigan

PARTICIPANTS

Carlos Jaramillo

Smithsonian Tropical Research Station

Brian Horton

University of Texas

Carmie Garzione

Rochester University

Hans ter Steege

Naturalis Biodiversity Center

Alex Correa-Metrio

Universidad Nacional Autonoma de Mexico

Catherine Rigsby

East Carolina University

Miles Silman

Wake Forest University

Christopher Dick

University of Michigan

Francisco Cruz

Universidade de So Paulo

Ana Carnaval City

University of New York

Andrew Eckert Virginia

Commonwealth University

Paul Baker

Duke University

Kyle Dexter

Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh

Stefano Manzoni

Duke University

Edgardo Latrubesse

University of Texas

Camila Ribas

Instituto Nacional de Pesquisas da Amazonia

Cleverson Silva

Universidade Federal Fluminense

David Battisti

University of Washington

Stephen Smith

University of Michigan

Mark Bush

Florida Institute of Technology

Jason Barnes

University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill

Carlos Peres

University of East Anglia

Norma Revillas

Universidad Nacional de San Antonio Abad del Cusco

Amilcare Porporato

Duke University

Nora Oleas

Universidad Tecnológica Indoamerica

Toby Pennington

Royal Botanical Garden Kew

Sherilyn Fritz

University of Nebraska - Lincoln

John Lundberg

Academy of Natural Sciences

COURSE

NEXT-GEN SEQUENCING: DATA ACQUISITION, COMPARATIVE GENOMICS, DESIGN AND ANALYSIS FOR POPULATION GENETICS, SYSTEMATICS AND DEVELOPMENT

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=282

DATES: 6/11/2012 - 6/19/2012

PI

Brian O'Connor

INSTITUTION

University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

COPI

James Noonan

Yale University

William Cresko

University of Oregon

Christine Elisk

Georgetown University

Konrad Paszkiewicz

University of Exeter

Alexie Papanicolaou

CSIRO

Greg Wray

Duke University

Jennifer Taylor

Australian National University

Jeffrey Townsend

Yale University

PARTICIPANTS

Konrad Paszkiewicz

University of Exeter

Jose Carlos Clemente Litran

University of Colorado-Boulder

Jeffrey Townsend

Yale University

Alexie Papanicolaou

Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation

Daniel McDonald

Biofrontiers Institute, CU-Boulder

Francesc Lopez Giraldez

Yale University

ANATOMY ONTOLOGIES IN EVOLUTIONARY BIOLOGY AND GENETICS

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=324

DATES: 7/30/2012 - 8/3/2012

PI

Melissa A Haendel

INSTITUTION

Oregon Health & Science University

COPI

Matthew Yoder

North Carolina State University

PARTICIPANTS

Melissa A Haendel

Oregon Health Sciences University

Robert Druzinsky

University of Illinois-Chicago

Eric Edsinger-Gonzales

University of California-Berkeley

Gaurav Vaidya

University of Colorado-Boulder

Thomas Alexander

Decechi McGill University

Michael Jansen

Arizona State University

Emmanuel Maxime

University of Louisiana-Lafayette

Christian Wirkner

Universitaet Rostock

Rambert Yan

New Jersey Institute of Technology

Alexis Hazbun

Medical University of South Carolina

Laura Moore

Oregon State University

COURSE, CONTINUED

John Cork	Louisiana State University Health Science Center, New Orleans
Erik Segerdell	Oregon Health & Science University
Carlo Torniai	Oregon Health & Science University
Jim P Balhoff	NESCent
Matthew Yoder	Illinois Natural History Survey
Terry Hayamizu	Jackson Laboratory
Nizar Ibrahim	University of Chicago
Yvonne Bradford	University of Oregon (Eugene,OR)
Jonathan Bard	University of Edinburgh

WORKSHOP ON EVOLUTIONARY QUANTITATIVE GENETICS

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=275

DATES: 8/6/2012 - 8/11/2012

PI

Stevan J Arnold

INSTITUTION

Oregon State University (Corvallis,OR)

COPI

Joseph Felsenstein

TBD (NC STATES)

PARTICIPANTS

Stevan J Arnold	Oregon State University (Corvallis,OR)
Liam Revell	University of Massachusetts-Boston
Luke Harmon	University of Idaho
Jonathan Losos	Harvard University
Joseph Felsenstein	University of Washington
Trudy Mackay	North Carolina State University
Adam Jones	Texas A & M University
Matt Pennell	NESCent
Marguerite Butler	University of Hawaii
Tanya Pennell	University of Sussex
Bridget Piculell	University of Mississippi
Nick Ratterman	Texas A & M University
Jason Smyth	Wake Forest University
Ahmed Moustafa	American University-Cairo
Geir Bolstad Norwegian	University of Science and Technology
Pedro Cordeiro-Estrela	Fundcao Oswaldo Cruz
Peter Fields	University of Virginia
Benjamin Hess	North Carolina Museum of Natural Sciences
Matthew Koski	University of Pittsburgh
Matt Marshall	University of North Carolina-Greensboro
Brooks Miner	Cornell University
Taylor Hundman	University of California-Riverside
Sumit Dhole	University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
Xiaoming Liu	University of Texas Health Science Center-Houston
Lauren Dembeck	North Carolina State University
Ricardo Wilches	Munich University
Noor White	Smithsonian Institution

COURSE, CONTINUED

Joel Adamson	University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
Barbara Fischer	University of Oslo
Aki Laruson	University of Hawaii-Manoa
Tami Cruikshank	Indiana University
Mira Han	Duke University
Masato Yamamichi	Cornell University

WORKING GROUP

SOFTWARE FOR BAYESIAN EVOLUTIONARY ANALYSIS BY SAMPLING TREES

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=191

DATES: 12/5/2011 - 12/8/2011

PI

Alexei Drummond

INSTITUTION

University of Auckland

COPI

Marc Suchard

University of California-Los Angeles

Andrew Rambaut

University of Edinburgh

PARTICIPANTS

Mandev Gil

University of California-Los Angeles

Sebastian Hoehna

Stockholm University

Daniel Ayres

University of Maryland-College Park

Remco Bouckaert

University of Auckland

Denise Kuehnert

University of Auckland

Tanja Stadler

ETH Zurich

Katia Koelle

Duke University

Philippe Lemey

Katholieke Universiteit Leuven

Jeff Thorne

North Carolina State University

David Swofford

NESCent

Peter Beerli

Florida State University

Alexander Alekseyenko

New York University School of Medicine

Paul Lewis

University of Connecticut

Trevor Bedford

University of Edinburgh

Guy Baele

Katholieke Universiteit Leuven

David Rasmussen

Duke University

Beth Shapiro

Pennsylvania State University

Samantha Lycett

University of Edinburgh

Marc Suchard

University of California-Los Angeles

Andrew Rambaut

University of Edinburgh

Alexei Drummond

NESCent

Benjamin D Redelings

NESCent

WORKING GROUP, CONTINUED

MODELING THE DIVERSIFICATION OF HUMAN LANGUAGES

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=255

DATES: 12/12/2011 - 12/14/2011

PI

Michael Gavin

INSTITUTION

Victoria University of Wellington

COPI

none

PARTICIPANTS

Gregor Yanega

NESCent

Adam Powell

UCL Genetics Institute

Russell Gray

University of Auckland

Jennifer Verdolin

NESCent

Joe McCarter

Victoria University of Wellington

Claire Bowers

Yale University

Rick Stepp

University of Florida

Rob Dunn

North Carolina State University

Robert Colwell

University of Connecticut

Thiago Rangel

Federal University of Goias

Michael Dunn

Max Planck Institute for Psycholinguistics

Carlos A. Botero

NESCent

Kathryn Kirby

University of Toronto

Sarah Tishkoff

University of Pennsylvania

Michael Gavin Victoria

University of Wellington

A WORKING GROUP TO SOLVE PROBLEMS IN MODEL SELECTION AND PHYLOGENY IN MIXED MULTI-FACTOR META-ANALYSIS

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=314

DATES: 1/12/2012 - 1/15/2012

PI

Jason Hoeksema

INSTITUTION

University of Mississippi

COPI

none

PARTICIPANTS

Juan C Santos

NESCent

Wittaya Kaonongbua

Indiana University

Jason Hoeksema

University of Mississippi

Wolfgang Viechtbauer

Maastricht University (Netherlands)

Bridget Piculell

University of Mississippi

Monique Gardes

University of Toulouse 3 - Paul Sabatier (France)

James Umbanhowar

University of North Carolina

Brook Milligan

New Mexico State University

WORKING GROUP, CONTINUED

Sounak Chakraborty	University of Missouri
Elizabeth Housworth	Indiana University
James Meadow	Montana State University
Brady Allred	Oklahoma State University
Jim Bever	Indiana University
Peter Zee	Indiana University
Bala Chaudhary	Northern Arizona University
Megan Rua	University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Marc Lajeunesse	University of South Florida

HIP: HACKATHONS, INTEROPERABILITY, PHYLOGENIES

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=294

DATES: 1/19/2012 - 1/21/2012

PI

Arlin Stoltzfus

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Center for Advanced Research in Biotechnology

COPI

Rutger Vos

University of Reading

Enrico Pontelli

New Mexico State University

PARTICIPANTS

Mark Westneat

Field Museum

Arlin Stoltzfus

Institute for Bioscience and Biotechnology Research

Enrico Pontelli

New Mexico State University

Rutger Vos

University of Reading

Hilmar Lapp

NESCent

Mark Wilkinson

University of British Columbia

Sergei Kosakovsky Pond

University of California-San Diego

Michael S Rosenberg

Arizona State University

Karen Cranston

NESCent

Brian L. Sidlauskas

Oregon State University

DETERMINANTS OF EXTINCTION IN ANCIENT AND MODERN SEAS

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=256

DATES: 1/19/2012 - 1/21/2012

PI

Paul G Harnik

INSTITUTION

Stanford University

COPI

Seth Finnegan

California Institute of Technology

Rowan Lockwood

College of William and Mary

PARTICIPANTS

Derek Tittensor

World Conservation Monitoring Center

Zoe Finkel

Mount Allison University

Heike Lotze

Dalhousie University

WORKING GROUP, CONTINUED

Lee Hsiang Liow	University of Oslo
John Pandolfi	University of Queensland
Seth Finnegan	California Institute of Technology
Jarrett Byrnes	National Center for Ecological Analysis and Synthesis
Jenny L McGuire	NESCent
Aaron O'Dea	Smithsonian Tropical Research Institute
David Lindberg	University of California Berkeley
Emily Orzechowski	College of William & Mary
Carl Simpson	Humboldt University Berlin
Rowan Lockwood	College of William and Mary
Paul G Harnik	NESCent
Sean Anderson	Dalhousie University

EVOCI TOOLKIT: CONCEPT INVENTORIES TO ASSESS CONCEPTUAL UNDERSTANDING OF EVOLUTION

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=258

DATES: 2/6/2012 - 2/9/2012

PI

Rebecca Price

INSTITUTION

University of Washington-Bothell

COPI

Kathryn Perez

University of Wisconsin at La Crosse

PARTICIPANTS

Mike Smith Mercer

University School of Medicine

Gregory Davis

Bryn Mawr College

Ryan Walker

University of Arkansas

Tessa Andrews

Montana State University

Anna Hiatt

Oklahoma State University

Jory P Weintraub

NESCent

Anastasia Thanukos

University of California

Louise Mead

National Center for Science Education

Terri McElhinny

Michigan State University

Joel Abraham

California State University-Fullerton

Kathryn Perez

University of Wisconsin, La Crosse

Rebecca Price

University of Washington-Bothell

Kathleen Fisher

San Diego State University, Semantic Research, Inc

Caleb Trujillo

Purdue University

LARGE-SCALE DEMOGRAPHIC, NETWORK AND BEHAVIORAL TRAIT ANALYSES OF SOCIALITY

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=285

DATES: 2/17/2012 - 2/19/2012

PI

Jennifer Fewell

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Arizona State University

COPI

James H Hunt

North Carolina State University

Dustin Rubenstein

Columbia University

WORKING GROUP, CONTINUED

PARTICIPANTS

Mike Wade	Indiana University
Jennifer Verdolin	NESCent
Collin McCabe	Harvard University
Dustin Rubenstein	Columbia University
James H Hunt	NC State University
Jennifer Fewell	Arizona State University
Sarah Zehr	Duke Lemur Center
Joshua Gibson	Arizona State University
James Costa	Highlands Biological Station & Western Carolina University
Eileen Lacey	University of California-Berkeley
Andy Russell	University of Exeter
Ferenc Jordan	University of Trento
Maurício Gonzalez-	Forero Univ. Tennessee
Carlos A. Botero	North Carolina State University
Patrick Abbot	Vanderbilt University

THE PERILS OF BEING BIPEDAL: AN EVOLUTIONARY PERSPECTIVE ON HUMAN MUSCULOSKELETAL DISORDERS

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=316

DATES: 3/14/2012 - 3/15/2012

PI

Bruce Latimer

INSTITUTION

Case Western Reserve University

COPI

Linda Spurlock

Cleveland Museum of Natural History

PARTICIPANTS

Rachel Caspari	Central Michigan University
Brian Corner	US Army Natick Soldier RDEC
Richard Drake	Cleveland Clinic Lerner College of Medicine
Karen Rosenberg	University of Delaware
Richard Sherwood	Wright State University
Chris Hernandez	Cornell University
Bruce Latimer	Case Western Reserve University
Carol Ward	University of Missouri
Meghan Cotter	Case Western Reserve University
Daniel Cooperman	University Hospitals-Cleveland
Linda Spurlock	Cleveland Museum of Natural History

WORKING GROUP, CONTINUED

ORIGINS OF C4 GRASSLANDS: A NEW SYNTHESIS OF PHYLOGENY, ECOLOGY AND PALEOBIOLOGY

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=260

DATES: 3/22/2012 - 3/26/2012

PI

Colin P Osborne

INSTITUTION

University of Sheffield

COPI

Christopher Still

University of California-Santa Barbara

Caroline A E Stromberg

University of Washington

PARTICIPANTS

Daniel Griffith

Wake Forest University (Winston-Salem,NC)

Beth Spriggs

Brown University

Pascal-Antoine

Christin Brown University

Caroline Lehmann

Macquarie University

Caroline A E Stromberg

University of Washington

Christopher Still

University of California-Santa Barbara

Benjamin H Passey

Johns Hopkins University

Michael Anderson

Wake Forest University

David Fox

University of Minnesota

Stephanie Pau

NCEAS

Colin P Osborne

University of Sheffield

Melinda Smith

Yale University

Erika J Edwards

Brown University

William Hoffmann

North Carolina State University

INFUSING MEDICAL EDUCATION WITH EVOLUTIONARY THINKING

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=315

DATES: 3/22/2012 - 3/25/2012

PI

Mark Schwartz

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New York University School of Medicine

COPI

Peter T Ellison

Harvard Univeristy

PARTICIPANTS

William Aird

BIDMC Harvard Medical School (BOSTON,MA)

Jory P Weintraub

NESCent

James S Chisholm

University of Western Australia

Mark Schwartz

New York University School of Medicine

Peter T Ellison

Harvard University

Magdalena Hurtado

Arizona State University

Joseph L Graves Jr

North Carolina A & T State University

Judy Scotchmoor

University of California-Berkeley

Athena Aktipos

University of California, San Francisco; Arizona State University

Barbara Natterson-Horowitz

University of California, Los Angeles

Brandon Hidaka

University of Kansas Medical Center

Gillian Bentley

Durham University

WORKING GROUP, CONTINUED

Randolph Nesse	University of Michigan
Cynthia M Beall	Case Western Reserve University
Stephen Stearns	Yale University
Andrew Read	Pennsylvania State University
Terry Wolpaw	Case Western Reserve University School of Medicine
Chris Reiber	State University of New York-Binghamton
Katelyn Bennett	New York University School of Medicine

SYNTHESIZING AND DATABASING FOSSIL CALIBRATIONS: DIVERGENCE DATING AND BEYOND

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=259

DATES: 3/29/2012 - 4/1/2012

PI

Daniel Ksepka

INSTITUTION

North Carolina State University

COPI

James Parham

Alabama Museum of Natural History, University of Alabama,

PARTICIPANTS

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North Carolina State University

N. Adam Smith

University of Wisconsin

P. David Polly

Indiana University

Jessica Ware

American Museum of Natural History/Rutgers University

Nathan Smith

The Field Museum of Natural History

Randall Irmis

University of Utah

Kristin Lamm

North Carolina State University

Elizabeth Hermsen

Cornell University

Marcel van Tuinen

University of North Carolina-Wilmington

Jose Patane

Instituto Butantan

James Parham

California State University-Bakersfield

Rachel Warnock

University of Bristol

INTEGRATIVE MODELS OF VERTEBRATE SOCIALITY: EVOLUTION, MECHANISM AND EMERGENT PROPERTIES

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=259

DATES: 3/29/2012 - 4/1/2012

PI

Dustin Rubenstein

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Columbia University

COPI

Eileen Lacey

University of California, Berkeley

Nancy Solomon

Miami University

Steve Phelps

University of Texas, Arlington

PARTICIPANTS

Dustin Rubenstein

Columbia University

Michael Taborsky

Institute of Ecology and Evolution, University of Bern

Jim Goodson

Indiana University

Nancy Solomon

Miami University

Larry Young

Emory University

WORKING GROUP, CONTINUED

Daniel Blumstein	University of California-Los Angeles
Steve Phelps	University of Texas-Austin
Annaliese Beery	Smith College
Loren Hayes	University of Tennessee at Chattanooga
Iain Couzin	Princeton University
Hans Hofmann	University of Texas-Austin
Emilia Martins	Indiana University

MODELING THE DIVERSIFICATION OF HUMAN LANGUAGES

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=255

DATES: 4/27/2012 - 4/29/2012

PI

Michael Gavin

INSTITUTION

Victoria University of Wellington

COPI

none

PARTICIPANTS

Michael Gavin	Colorado State University
Adam Powell	UCL Genetics Institute
Jennifer Verdolin	NESCent
Kathryn Kirby	University of Toronto
Claire Bowern	Yale University
Gregor Yanega	Unaffiliated
Rick Stepp	University of Florida
Russell Gray	The University of Auckland
Michelle Trautwein	Nature Research Center, North Carolina Museum of Natural
Rob Dunn	North Carolina State University
Robert Colwell	Univ. of Connecticut
Carlos A. Botero	North Carolina State University
Thiago Rangel	Universidade Federal de Goiás

THE TREE OF SEX – A COMPREHENSIVE SYNTHESIS OF SEX DETERMINATION SYSTEMS IN EUKARYOTES

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=291

DATES: 5/14/2012 - 5/18/2012

PI

Doris Bachtrog

INSTITUTION

University of California, Berkeley

COPI

Judith Mank

University of Oxford

Catherine Peichel

Fred Hutchinson Cancer Research Center

PARTICIPANTS

Matthew Hahn	Indiana University
Laura Ross	University of Oxford
Itay Mayrose	Tel Aviv University
Jun Kitano	National Institute of Genetics
Jana Vamosi	University of Calgary
Ray Ming	University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

CATALYSIS MEETINGS, CONTINUED

Sarah Otto	University of British Columbia [Currently on sabbatical]
Nicole Valenzuela	Iowa State University
Tia-Lynn Ashman	University of Pittsburgh
Doris Bachtrog	University of California, Berkeley
Catherine Peichel	Fred Hutchinson Cancer Research Center
Judith Mank	University College London
Nicolas Perrin	University of Lausanne

TEMPO AND MODE OF PLANT TRAIT EVOLUTION: SYNTHESIZING DATA FROM EXTANT AND EXTINCT TAXA

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=269

DATES: 5/21/2012 - 5/25/2012

<u>PI</u>	<u>INSTITUTION</u>
William Cornwell	UC Berkeley
<u>COPI</u>	
Amy Zanne	University of Missouri-St. Louis
Stephen Smith	Brown University
<u>PARTICIPANTS</u>	
Luke Harmon	University of Idaho
Brad Oberle	University of Missouri
Cody Hinchliff	University of Michigan
Peter Stevens	University of Missouri
Brian C O'Meara	University of Tennessee
Rich FitzJohn	University of British Columbia
Daniel McGlinn	Utah State University
Matt Pennell	University of Idaho
Hafiz Maherali	University of Guelph
David Tank	University of Idaho
Stephen Smith	Brown University
Risa Sargent	University of Ottawa
Amy Zanne	University of Missouri
Jonathan Eastman	University of Idaho
William Cornwell	Vrije Universiteit
Jeremy Beaulieu	Yale University

HIP: HACKATHONS, INTEROPERABILITY, PHYLOGENIES

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=294

DATES: 6/4/2012 - 6/8/2012

<u>PI</u>	<u>INSTITUTION</u>
Arlin Stoltzfus	Center for Advanced Research in Biotechnology
<u>COPI</u>	
Rutger Vos	University of Reading
Enrico Pontelli	New Mexico State University
<u>PARTICIPANTS</u>	
Naim Matasci	iPlant Collaborative
Aaron Steele	University of California-Berkeley

WORKING GROUP, CONTINUED

Campbell O Webb	Harvard University
Jeet Sukumaran	Duke University
Enrico Pontelli	New Mexico State University
Jim P Balhoff	NESCent
Hilmar Lapp	NESCent
Siavash Mirarab	University of Texas-Austin
Chris Baron	Field Museum
Gaurav Vaidya	University of Colorado at Boulder
Tracy Heath	University of California-Berkeley
Mark Holder	University of Kansas
Karen Cranston	NESCent
Emily Jane McTavish	University of Texas-Austin
Arlin Stoltzfus	Institute for Bioscience and Biotechnology Research
Holly Bik	University of California-Davis
Ben Vandervalk	University of British Columbia
Megan Pirrung	University of Colorado
Christian M. Zmasek	Sanford-Burnham Medical Research Institute
Rutger Vos	NCB Naturalis
Helena Deus	Digital Enterprise Research Institute
James Estill	University of Georgia
Peter E Midford	NESCent

ENVIRONMENTAL AND DEMOGRAPHIC DETERMINANTS OF NATURAL SELECTION

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=326

DATES: 7/12/2012 - 7/14/2012

<u>PI</u>	<u>INSTITUTION</u>
Andrew MacColl	School of Biology
<u>COPI</u>	
Adam Siepielski	University of San Diego
Tim Coulson	Imperial College of London
Stephanie Carlson	University California-Berkeley
<u>PARTICIPANTS</u>	
Tim Coulson	Imperial College
Ben Sheldon	University of Oxford
Michael Morrissey	University of St Andrews
Stephanie Carlson	University of California-Berkeley
Sonya Clegg	Griffith University
Adam Siepielski	University of San Diego
Mike Wade	Indiana University
Shripad Tuljapurkar	Stanford University
Mathieu Buoro	University of California-Berkeley
Christina M Caruso	University of Guelph
Nina Sletvold	Uppsala University
Joe Hereford	University of Maryland
Andrew MacColl	University of Nottingham

WORKING GROUP, CONTINUED

Erik Svensson	Lund University
Loeske Kruuk	University of Edinburgh
Clinton D Francis	NESCent
Joel Kingsolver	University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

EVOCI TOOLKIT: CONCEPT INVENTORIES TO ASSESS CONCEPTUAL UNDERSTANDING OF EVOLUTION

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=258

DATES: 7/24/2012 - 7/27/2012

PI

Rebecca Price

INSTITUTION

University of Washington-Bothell

COPI

Kathryn Perez

University of Wisconsin at La Crosse

PARTICIPANTS

Joel Abraham

California State University-Fullerton

Terri McElhinny

Michigan State University

Louise S Mead

Michigan State University

Gregory Davis

Bryn Mawr College

Mark Terry

Northwest School

Mike Smith Mercer

University School of Medicine

Caleb Trujillo

Purdue University

Ryan Walker

University of Arkansas

Tessa Andrews

University of Georgia

Anna Hiatt

Oklahoma State University

Kathryn Perez

University of Wisconsin

Anastasia Thanukos

University of California

Rebecca Price

University of Washington-Bothell

A WORKING GROUP TO SOLVE PROBLEMS IN MODEL SELECTION AND PHYLOGENY IN MIXED MULTI-FACTOR META-ANALYSIS

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=314

DATES: 8/16/2012 - 8/19/2012

PI

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University of Mississippi

COPI

none

PARTICIPANTS

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University of South Florida

Elizabeth

Housworth Indiana University

James Umbanhowar

University of North Carolina

Jim Bever

Indiana University

James Meadow

University of Oregon

Megan Rua

University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill

Bridget Piculell

University of Mississippi

WORKING GROUP, CONTINUED

Wolfgang Viechtbauer	Maastricht University
Monique Gardes	University of Toulouse 3 - Paul Sabatier (France)
Sounak Chakraborty	University of Missouri
Brook Milligan	New Mexico State University
Peter Zee	Indiana University

MODELING THE DIVERSIFICATION OF HUMAN LANGUAGES

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=255

DATES: 8/30/2012 - 9/1/2012

PI

Michael Gavin Victoria

INSTITUTION

University of Wellington

COPI

none

PARTICIPANTS

Robert Colwell	Univ. of Connecticut
Rick Stepp	University of Florida
Russell Gray	The University of Auckland
Kathryn Kirby	University of British Columbia
Michael Gavin	Colorado State University
Joe McCarter	Colorado State University
Adam Powell	UCL Genetics Institute
Jennifer Verdolin	NESCent
Gregor Yanega	Unaffiliated
Claire Bower	Yale University
Michelle Trautwein	North Carolina State University
Thiago Rangel	Universidade Federal de Gois
Rob Dunn	North Carolina State University
Carlos A. Botero	North Carolina State University

DETERMINANTS OF EXTINCTION IN ANCIENT AND MODERN SEAS

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=256

DATES: 9/13/2012 - 9/16/2012

PI

Paul G Harnik

INSTITUTION

Stanford University

COPI

Seth Finnegan

California Institute of Technology

Rowan Lockwood

College of William and Mary

PARTICIPANTS

Aaron O'Dea	Smithsonian Tropical Research Institute
Emily Orzechowski	College of William & Mary
Seth Finnegan	University of California Berkeley
David Lindberg	University of California Berkeley
Derek Tittensor	Dalhousie University
Heike Lotze	Dalhousie University

WORKING GROUP, CONTINUED

John Pandolfi	University of Queensland
Jarrett Byrnes	UMass Boston
Rowan Lockwood	College of William & Mary
Lee Hsiang Liow	University of Oslo
Jenny McGuire	University of Washington
Paul G Harnik	NESCent
Carl Simpson	Humboldt University Berlin
Craig R McClain	NESCent
Zoe Finkel	Mount Allison University
Sean Anderson	Simon Fraser University

LEARNING EVOLUTION FROM THE FOSSIL RECORD: K-12 EXPLORATIONS IN DEEP TIME

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=345

DATES: 9/21/2012 - 9/24/2012

PI

Margaret Yacobucci

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Bowling Green State University (Bowling Green,OH)

COPI

Pedro Marengo

Bryn Mawr College

Roy Plotnick

University of Illinois (Chicago)

Dena Smith

University of Colorado

PARTICIPANTS

Pedro Marengo

Bryn Mawr College

Margaret Yacobucci

Bowling Green State University (Bowling Green,OH)

Christopher Miller

University of Illinois-Chicago

Roy Plotnick

University of Illinois-Chicago

Lisa White

University of California-Berkeley (Berkeley,CA)

Stacey Forsyth

University of Colorado-Boulder

Olayinka Mohorn-Mintah

University of Illinois-Chicago

Jane Pickering

Yale Peabody Museum

Dena Smith

University of Colorado-Boulder

Wendy Jackson

DePaul University

Alice Lesnick

Bryn Mawr College

LARGE-SCALE DEMOGRAPHIC, NETWORK AND BEHAVIORAL TRAIT ANALYSES OF SOCIALITY

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=285

DATES: 9/27/2012 - 9/30/2012

PI

Jennifer Fewell

INSTITUTION

Arizona State University

COPI

James H Hunt

North Carolina State University

Dustin Rubenstein

Columbia University

PARTICIPANTS

Judith Korb

University of Osnabrueck

Mauricio Gonzalez-Forero

Univ. Tennessee

Patrick Abbot

Vanderbilt University

WORKING GROUP, CONTINUED

James H Hunt	NC State University
Jennifer Verdolin	NESCent
Dustin Rubenstein	Columbia University
Mike Wade	Indiana University
Andy Russell	University of Exeter
Charles Nunn	Harvard University
Collin McCabe	Harvard University
Ferenc Jordan	University of Trento
Carlos A. Botero	NESCent
Jennifer Fewell	Arizona State University

SYNTHESIZING AND DATABASING FOSSIL CALIBRATIONS: DIVERGENCE DATING AND BEYOND

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=259

DATES: 10/12/2012 - 10/14/2012

PI

Daniel Ksepka

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North Carolina State University

COPI

James Parham

Alabama Museum of Natural History, University of Alabama

PARTICIPANTS

Philip Donoghue

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Marcel van Tuinen

University of North Carolina-Wilmington

Rachel Warnock

NESCent

N. Adam Smith

NESCent

Nathan Smith

Howard University

Karen Cranston

NESCent

Daniel Ksepka

North Carolina State University

Kristin Lamm

NESCent

Jim Allman

Interrobang Digital Media

P. David Polly

Indiana University

Jessica Ware

Rutgers University-Newark

Maria Gandolfo Nixon

Cornell University

Randall Irmis

University of Utah

Elizabeth Hermesen

Ohio University

Mike Benton

University of Bristol

Jason Head

University of Nebraska-Lincoln

James Parham

Alabama Museum of Natural History, University of Alabama

EVOLUTIONARY MISMATCH AND WHAT TO DO ABOUT IT

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=261

DATES: 10/12/2012 - 10/13/2012

PI

David Wilson

INSTITUTION

Binghamton University

COPI

none

WORKING GROUP, CONTINUED

PARTICIPANTS

Jerry Miller	Evolution Institute
Sean Valles	Michigan State University
Bruce Robertson	Bard College
Jennifer Verdolin	NESCent
Sudhindra Rao	Binghamton University
Elisabeth Lloyd	Indiana University
Joseph L Graves Jr	North Carolina A&T State University
Marco Del Giudice	University of Torino
Terry Burnham	Chapman University
David Wilson	Binghamton University

INTEGRATIVE MODELS OF VERTEBRATE SOCIALITY: EVOLUTION, MECHANISM AND EMERGENT PROPERTIES

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=257

DATES: 10/18/2012 - 10/21/2012

PI

Dustin Rubenstein

COPI

Eileen Lacey

Nancy Solomon

Steve Phelps

PARTICIPANTS

Michael Taborsky

Hans Hofmann

Daniel Blumstein

Jim Goodson

Dustin Rubenstein

Larry Young

Nancy Solomon

Emilia Martins

Steve Phelps

Peter Hurd

Eileen Lacey

Ryan Earley

Iain Couzin

Loren Hayes

John Wingfield

Annaliese Beery

INSTITUTION

Columbia University

University of California, Berkeley

Miami University

University of Texas, Arlington

University of Bern

The University of Texas-Austin

University of California-Los Angeles

Indiana University

Columbia University

Emory University

Miami University

Indiana University

University of Texas-Austin

University of Alberta

University of California-Berkeley

University of Alabama

Princeton University

University of Louisiana-Monroe

University of California-Davis

Smith College

COURSES

EVOLUTION 2012 - A WORKSHOP FOR EDUCATORS

URL: http://www.nescent.org/cal/calendar_detail.php?id=857

DATES: 8/13/2012 - 8/15/2012

PI

Greg Gibson

INSTITUTION

North Carolina State University

COPI

none

PARTICIPANTS

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GMOD SUMMER TRAINING 2012

URL: http://www.nescent.org/cal/calendar_detail.php?id=885

DATES: 8/25/2012 - 8/29/2012

PI

Todd Vision

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none

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OTHER MEETINGS

DRYADLAB WORKSHOP

URL: http://www.nescent.org/cal/calendar_detail.php?id=788

DATES: 12/1/2011 - 12/4/2011

PI

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none

PARTICIPANTS

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IT TOWNHALL MEETING

URL: http://www.nescent.org/cal/calendar_detail.php?id=790

DATES: 12/8/2011 - 12/8/2011

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PHYLOINFORMATICS FOUNDATION BOARD

URL: http://www.nescent.org/cal/calendar_detail.php?id=787

DATES: 12/12/2011 - 12/14/2011

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none

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David Maddison

Oregon State University

Val Tannen

University of Pennsylvania

Rutger Vos

University of Reading

Mark Westneat

Field Museum

Karen Cranston

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William Piel

Yale University

Michael Donoghue

Yale University

OTHER MEETINGS

NESCENT ADVISORY BOARD

URL: http://www.nescent.org/cal/calendar_detail.php?id=805

DATES: 2/2/2012 - 2/3/2012

PI

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none

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Blaire Van Valkenburgh

University of California

Mark Stoneking

Max Planck - Evolutionary Anthropology

Stephen Stearns

Yale University

Ana Rivero

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Richard Ree

Field Museum

Weigang Qiu

Hunter College

Carlo Maley

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Vicki A Funk

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Peter T Ellison

Harvard University

Adriana Briscoe

University of Calif - Irvine

Joseph L Graves Jr

North Carolina A&T State University

PHENOSCAPE MEETING

URL: http://www.nescent.org/cal/calendar_detail.php?id=833

DATES: 4/25/2012 - 4/27/2012

PI

Paula Mabee

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none

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University at Buffalo

Brian Hall

Dalhousie University

OTHER MEETINGS

DRYAD TEAM MEETING

URL: http://www.nescent.org/cal/calendar_detail.php?id=849

DATES: 4/22/2012 - 4/23/2012

PI

Todd Vision

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University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

COPI

none

PARTICIPANTS

Todd Vision

UNC Chapel Hill

OPENTREE AVATOL MEETING

URL: http://www.nescent.org/cal/calendar_detail.php?id=853

DATES: 5/15/2012 - 5/17/2012

PI

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none

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Romina Gazis

Clark University

Mark Holder

University of Kansas

David Hibbett

Clark University

Gordon Burleigh

University of Florida

Tiffani Williams

Texas A&M University

Stephen Smith

University of Michigan

Richard Ree

Field Museum of Natural History

Laura Katz

Smith College

Douglas Soltis

University of Florida

Keith Crandall

Brigham Young University

MAPPING NESCENT'S FUTURE

URL: http://www.nescent.org/cal/calendar_detail.php?id=836

DATES: 5/24/2012 - 5/25/2012

PI

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none

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Armin Moczek

University of Indiana

Sudhir Kumar

Arizona State University

OTHER MEETINGS

Allen Rodrigo	NESCent
Todd Vision	UNC Chapel Hill
Edmund Brodie	University of Virginia
Emilie Snell-Rood	University of Minnesota-Twin Cities
Felisa A Smith	University of New Mexico
Jack Sullivan	University of Idaho
Matthew Wund	The College of New Jersey
Rob Guralnick	University of Colorado
Sonia E Sultan	Wesleyan University
Joel Kingsolver	University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
Carlos Botero	North Carolina State University

DRYAD BOARD OF DIRECTORS MEETING

URL: http://www.nescent.org/cal/calendar_detail.php?id=839

DATES: 7/23/2012 - 7/25/2012

PI

Todd Vision

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University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

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none

PARTICIPANTS

Eefke Smit	International Association of STM Publishers
Peggy Schaeffer	NESCent
Lee Dirks	Microsoft Research Connections
Theodora Bloom	Public Library of Science (PLOS)
Liz Ferguson	Wiley-Blackwell
Simon Hodson	JISC
Marcel Holyoak	University of California
Brian Lavoie	OCLC
William Michener	University of New Mexico
Todd Vision	University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
Allen Moore	University of Georgia
Susanna-Assunta Sansone	University of Oxford
Michael Whitlock	University of British Columbia

NESCENT ADVISORY BOARD

URL: http://www.nescent.org/cal/calendar_detail.php?id=863

DATES: 9/13/2012 - 9/14/2012

PI

Joseph L Graves Jr

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none

PARTICIPANTS

EBlair Van Valkenburgh	University of California
Allen Rodrigo	NESCent

OTHER MEETINGS

Ana Rivero	CNRS
Jory P Weintraub	NESCent
Jenny Xiang	NESCent
Vicki A Funk	Smithsonian
Peter T Ellison	Harvard University
Adriana Briscoe	University of Calif - Irvine
Susan C Alberts	NESCent
Weigang Qiu	Hunter College
Carlo Maley	University of California-San Francisco
Todd Vision	NESCent
Richard Ree	Field Museum
Craig R McClain	NESCent

DRYAD BOARD OF DIRECTORS 2012

URL: http://www.nescent.org/cal/calendar_detail.php?id=897

DATES: 11/17/2012 - 11/18/2012

PI

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none

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Todd Vision	NESCent
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William Michener	University of New Mexico
Allen Moore	University of Georgia
Peggy Schaeffer	NESCent

APPENDIX G:

PUBLICATIONS FROM NESCENT SUPPORTED PROJECTS IN YEAR 8

1. Allen KL, Kay RF (2012) Dietary quality and encephalization in platyrrhine primates. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 279: 715-721.
2. Andrews T, Price R, Mead L, McElhinny T, Thanukos A, et al. (2012) Biology undergraduates' misconceptions about genetic drift. *CBE—Life Sciences Education* 11: 248-259.
3. Antolin MF, Jenkins KP, Bergstrom CT, Crespi BJ, De S, et al. (2012) Evolution and medicine in undergraduate education: a prescription for all biology students. *Evolution* 66: 1991-2006.
4. Barrio-Amoros CL, Santos JC (2012) A phylogeny for Aromobates (Anura: Dendrobatidae) with description of three new species from the Andes of Venezuela, taxonomic comments on Aromobates saltuensis, A. inflexus, and notes on the conservation status of the genus. *Zootaxa*: 1-31.
5. Belinky F, Szitenberg A, Goldfarb I, Feldstein T, Worheide G, et al. (2012) ALG11 – a new variable DNA marker for sponge phylogeny. Comparison of phylogenetic performances with the 18S rDNA and the COI gene. *Molecular Phylogenetics & Evolution* 63: 702-713.
6. Bik HM, Porazinska DL, Creer S, Caporaso JG, Knight R, et al. (2012) Sequencing our way towards understanding global eukaryotic biodiversity. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 27: 233-243.
7. Bittles AH (2012) Consanguinity in Context. Cambridge: *Cambridge University Press*.
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9. Botero CA, Rubenstein DR (2012) Fluctuating environments, sexual selection and the evolution of flexible mate choice in birds. *PLoS ONE* 7: e32311.
10. Bouckaert R, Lemey P, Dunn M, Greenhill SJ, Alekseyenko AV, et al. (2012) Mapping the origins and expansion of the Indo-European language family. *Science* 337: 957-960.
11. Bromham L, Lanfear R, Cassey P, Gibb G, Cardillo M (2012) Reconstructing past species assemblages reveals the changing patterns and drivers of extinction through time. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B* <http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2012.1437>.
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16. Caruso CM, Maherali H, Benschoter AM (2012) Why are trade-offs between flower size and number infrequently detected? A test of three hypotheses. *International Journal of Plant Sciences* 173: 26-35.
17. Comas LH, Mueller KE, Taylor LL, Midford PE, Callahan HS, et al. (2012) Evolutionary Patterns and Biogeochemical Significance of Angiosperm Root Traits. *International Journal of Plant Sciences* 173: 584-595.
18. Cruickshank T, Wade MJ (2012) Maternal Adjustment of the Sex Ratio in Broods of the Broad-Horned Flour Beetle, *Gnathocerus cornutus*. *Integrative And Comparative Biology* 52: 100-107.
19. Cummings JR, Muchlinski MN, Kirk EC, Rehorek SJ, DeLeon VB, et al. (2012) Eye Size at Birth in Prosimian Primates: Life History Correlates and Growth Patterns. *PLoS ONE* 7.
20. Davis AM, Unmack PJ, Pusey BJ, Johnson JB, Pearson RG (2012) Marine-freshwater transitions are associated with the evolution of dietary diversification in terapontid grunters (Teleostei: Terapontidae). *Journal of Evolutionary Biology* 25: 1163-1179.
21. Deans AR, Yoder MJ, Balhoff JP (2012) Time to change how we describe biodiversity. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 27: 78-84.
22. Delaney N, Balenger S, Bonneaud C, Marx C, Hill G, et al. (2012) Ultrafast evolution and loss of CRISPRs following host shift in a novel wildlife pathogen, *Mycoplasma gallisepticum*. *PLoS Genetics* 8: e1002511.

PUBLICATIONS FROM NESCENT SUPPORTED PROJECTS IN YEAR 8, CONTINUED

23. Donohue K, Barua D, Butler C, Tisdale TE, Chiang GCK, et al. (2012) Maternal effects alter natural selection on phytochromes through seed germination. *Journal of Ecology* 100: 750-757.
24. Drenovsky R, Grewell B, D'Antonio C, Funk J, James J, et al. (2012) A functional trait perspective on plant invasion: invasiveness to impacts in a changing world. *Annals of Botany* 110: 141-153.
25. Drummond AJ, Suchard MA, Xie D, Rambaut A (2012) Bayesian Phylogenetics with BEAUti and the BEAST 1.7. *Molecular Biology and Evolution* 29: 1969-1973.
26. Durst PAP, Roth VL (2012) Classification Tree Methods Provide a Multifactorial Approach to Predicting Insular Body Size Evolution in Rodents. *American Naturalist* 179: 545-553.
27. Edrey YH, Casper D, Huchon D, Gelfond J, Mele J, et al. (2012) Sustained high levels of neuregulin-1 in the longest-lived rodents; a key determinant of rodent longevity. *Aging Cell* 11: 213-222.
28. Edwards EJ, Group GPW, Aliscioni S, Bell HL, Besnard G, et al. (2012) New grass phylogeny resolves deep evolutionary relationships and discovers C4 origins. *New Phytologist* 193: 304-312.
29. Erpenbeck D, Schmitz J, Churakov G, Huchon D, Worheide G, et al. (2012) First evidence of miniature transposable elements in sponges (Porifera). *Hydrobiologia* 687: 43-47.
30. Faria NR, Hodges-Mameletzis I, Silva JC, Rodes B, Erasmus S, et al. (2012) Phylogeographical footprint of colonial history in the global dispersal of human immunodeficiency virus type 2 group A. *Journal of General Virology* 93: 889-899.
31. Francis C, Blickley J (2012) Introduction: Research and perspectives on the study of anthropogenic noise and birds. in The Influence of Anthropogenic Noise on Birds and Bird Studies. *Ornithological Monographs (Auk Supplement)* 74.
32. Francis C, Kleist N, Davidson B, Ortega C, Cruz A (2012) Behavioral responses by two songbirds to natural gas well compressor noise. in The Influence of Anthropogenic Noise on Birds and Bird Studies. *Ornithological Monographs (Auk Supplement)* 74.
33. Francis C, Ortega C, Kennedy R, Nylander P (2012) Are predators unable to locate nests or are they absent from noisy areas? in The Influence of Anthropogenic Noise on Birds and Bird Studies. *Ornithological Monographs (Auk Supplement)* 74.
34. Francis CD, Kleist NJ, Ortega CP, Cruz A (2012) Noise pollution alters ecological services: enhanced pollination and disrupted seed dispersal. *Proceedings Of The Royal Society B-Biological Sciences* 279: 2727-2735.
35. Fritsch PW, Cruz BC (2012) Phylogeny of *Cercis* based on DNA sequences of nuclear ITS and four plastid regions: Implications for transatlantic historical biogeography. *Molecular Phylogenetics & Evolution* 62: 816-825.
36. Gelfman S, Burstein D, Penn O, Savchenko A, Amit M, et al. (2012) Changes in exon-intron structure during vertebrate evolution affect the splicing pattern of exons. *Genome Research* 22: 35-50.
37. Groover A, Dosmann M (2012) The importance of living botanical collections for plant biology and the "next generation" of evo-devo research. *Frontiers in Plant Evolution and Development* 3.
38. Groover A, Jansson S (2012) Comparative and evolutionary genomics of forest trees. In: Fenning T, editor. Challenges and opportunities for the world's forests in the 21st century. Scotland, UK.
39. Gschwend AR, Weingartner LA, Moore RC, Ming R (2012) The sex-specific region of sex chromosomes in animals and plants. *Chromosome Research* 20: 57-69.
40. Han MV (2012) Characterizing gene movements between chromosomes in *Drosophila*. *Fly* 6: 121-125.
41. Han MV, Hahn MW (2012) Inferring the History of Interchromosomal Gene Transposition in *Drosophila* Using n-Dimensional Parsimony. *Genetics* 190: 813- 825.
42. Hansen MM, Olivieri I, Waller DM, Nielsen EE, GeM. Working Grp (2012) Monitoring adaptive genetic responses to environmental change. *Molecular Ecology* 21: 1311-1329.
43. Harnik P, Lotze H, Anderson S, Finkel Z, Finnegan S, et al. (2012) Extinctions in ancient and modern seas. *Trends in Ecology and Evolution*.
44. Hoeksema J, Hernandez J, Rogers D, Mendoza L, Thompson J (2012) Geographic divergence in a species-rich symbiosis: Interactions between Monterey pines and ectomycorrhizal fungi. *Ecology* in press, early view avail.
45. Hunt JH (2012) A conceptual model for the origin of worker behaviour and adaptation of eusociality. *Journal of Evolutionary Biology* 25: 1-19.
46. Jackson JA, Laikre L, Baker CS, Kendall KC, Genetic Monitoring Working Grp (2012) Guidelines for collecting and maintaining archives for genetic monitoring. *Conservation Genetics Resources* 4: 527-536.

PUBLICATIONS FROM NESCENT SUPPORTED PROJECTS IN YEAR 8, CONTINUED

47. Johnson NA, Lahti DC, Blumstein DT (2012) Combating the assumption of evolutionary progress: Lessons from the decay and loss of traits. *Evolution: Education and Outreach* 5: 128-138.
48. Johnson NA, Smith JJ, Pobiner B, Schrein C (2012) Why are chimps still chimps? *American Biology Teacher* 74: 74-80.
49. Law SHW, Redelings BD, Kullman SW (2012) Comparative Genomics of Duplicate gamma-Glutamyl Transferase Genes in Teleosts: Medaka (*Oryzias latipes*), Stickleback (*Gasterosteus aculeatus*), Green Spotted Pufferfish (*Tetraodon nigroviridis*), Fugu (*Takifugu rubripes*), and Zebrafish (*Danio rerio*). *Journal of Experimental Zoology Part B: Molecular & Developmental Evolution* 318B: 35-49.
50. Ledon- Rettig C, Richards C, Martin L (2012) Epigenetics for behavioral ecologists. *Behavioral Ecology* In press.
51. Lens A, Cooper L, Gandolfo M, Groover A, Jaiswal P, et al. (2012) An extension of the plant ontology project supporting wood anatomy and development research. *IAWA Journal* 33: 113-117.
52. Liberles DA, Teichmann SA, Bahar I, Bastolla U, Bloom J, et al. (2012) The interface of protein structure, protein biophysics, and molecular evolution. *Protein Science* 21: 769-785.
53. Lovette IJ, Arbogast BS, Curry RL, Zink RM, Botero CA, et al. (2012) Phylogenetic Relationships of the Mockingbirds and Thrashers (Aves: Mimidae). *Molecular Phylogenetics & Evolution* 63: 219-229.
54. Mabee P, Balhoff JP, Dahdul WM, Lapp H, Midford PE, et al. (2012) 500,000 fish phenotypes: The new informatics landscape for evolutionary and developmental biology of the vertebrate skeleton. *Journal of Applied Ichthyology* 28: 300-305.
55. MacLean EL, Matthews LJ, Hare BA, Nunn CL, Anderson RC, et al. (2012) How does cognition evolve? Phylogenetic comparative psychology. *Animal Cognition* 15: 223-238.
56. McClain C, Allen A, Tittensor D, Rex M (2012) The energetics of life on the deep sea floor. *PNAS*.
57. McClain CR (2012) Increased energy promotes size-based niche availability in marine mollusks. *Integrative & Comparative Biology* 52: E117-E117.
58. McClain CR, Gullett T, Jackson-Ricketts J, Unmack PJ (2012) Increased Energy Promotes Size-Based Niche Availability in Marine Mollusks. *Evolution* 66: 2204- 2215.
59. McClain CR, Stegen JC, Hurlbert AH (2012) Dispersal, environmental niches and oceanic-scale turnover in deep-sea bivalves. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 279: 1993-2002.
60. Meachen JA, Samuels JX (2012) Evolution in coyotes (*Canis latrans*) in response to the megafaunal extinctions. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 109: 4191-4196.
61. Meachen-Samuels JA (2012) Morphological convergence of the prey-killing arsenal of sabertooth predators. *Paleobiology* 38: 1-14.
62. Medina I, Francis C (2012) Environmental variability and acoustic signals: a multilevel approach in songbirds. *Biology Letters*.
63. Mideo N, Acosta-Serrano A, Aebischer T, Brown MJ, Fenton A, et al. (2012) Life in cells, hosts, and vectors: parasite evolution across scales. *Infection, Genetics & Evolution* (in press, corrected proof available).
64. Mideo NM, Reece SE (2012) Plasticity in parasite phenotypes: evolutionary and ecological implications for disease. *Future Microbiology* 7: 17-24.
65. Miko I, Friedrich F, Yoder MJ, Hines HM, Deitz LL, et al. (2012) On dorsal prothoracic appendages in treehoppers (Hemiptera: Membracidae) and the nature of morphological evidence. *PLoS ONE* 7: e30137.
66. Moczek AP (2012) The nature of nurture and the causes of traits: toward a comprehensive theory of developmental evolution. *Integrative & Comparative Biology* 52: E123.
67. Moczek AP (2012) The Nature of Nurture and the Future of Evodevo: Toward a Theory of Developmental Evolution. *Integrative And Comparative Biology* 52: 108-119.
68. Murren CJ (2012) The Integrated Phenotype. *Integrative And Comparative Biology* 52: 64-76.
69. Near TJ, Sandel M, Kuhn KL, Unmack PJ, Wainwright PC, et al. (2012) Nuclear gene-inferred phylogenies resolve the relationships of the enigmatic Pygmy Sunfishes, *Elassoma* (Teleostei: Percomorpha). *Molecular Phylogenetics & Evolution* 63: 388-395.
70. Ortega C, Francis C (2012) The influence of anthropogenic noise on point count detections: implications for surveys in a variety of habitats. in *The Influence of Anthropogenic Noise on Birds and Bird Studies. Ornithological Monographs (Auk Supplement)* 74.
71. Page TJ, Marshall JC, Hughes JM (2012) The world in a grain of sand: evolutionarily relevant, small-scale freshwater bioregions on subtropical dune islands. *Freshwater Biology* 57: 612-627.

PUBLICATIONS FROM NESCENT SUPPORTED PROJECTS IN YEAR 8, CONTINUED

72. Parham JF, Donoghue PCJ, Bell CJ, Calway TD, Head JJ, et al. (2012) Best practices for justifying fossil calibrations. *Systematic Biology* 61: 346-359.
73. Plotnick RE (2012) Behavioral biology of trace fossils. *Paleobiology* 38: 459-473.
74. Plotnick RE, Smith DM (2012) Exceptionally Preserved Fossil Insect Ears from the Eocene Green River Formation of Colorado. *Journal of Paleontology* 86: 19-24.
75. Pollitt LC, Reece SE, Mideo N, Nussey DH, N. C (2012) The problem of autocorrelation in parasitology. *PLoS Pathogens* 8: e1002590.
76. Popescu AA, Huber KT, Paradis E (2012) ape 3.0: New tools for distance-based phylogenetics and evolutionary analysis in R. *Bioinformatics* 28: 1536-1537.
77. Price SA, Hopkins SSB, Smith KK, Roth VL (2012) Tempo of trophic evolution and its impact on mammalian diversification. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 109: 7008-7012.
78. Privman E, Penn O, Pupko T (2012) Improving the performance of positive selection inference by filtering unreliable alignment regions. *Molecular Biology & Evolution* 29: 1-5.
79. Revell LJ, Mahler DL, Peres-Neto PR, Redelings BD (2012) A New Phylogenetic Method for Identifying Exceptional Phenotypic Diversification. *Evolution* 66: 135- 146.
80. Ribas CC, Aleixo A, Nogueira ACR, Miyaki CY, Cracraft J (2012) A palaeobiogeographic model for biotic diversification within Amazonia over the past three million years. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 279: 681-689.
81. Richards C, Schrey A, Pigliucci M (2012) Invasion of diverse habitats by few Japanese knotweed genotypes is correlated with high epigenetic differentiation. *Ecology Letters* 15: 1016-1025.
82. Richards C, Verhoeven K, Bossdorf O (2012) Evolutionary significance of epigenetic variation. In: Wendel J, editor. *Plant Genome Diversity*: Springer.
83. Rifkin JL, Nunn CL, Garamszegi LZ (2012) Do Animals Living in Larger Groups Experience Greater Parasitism? A Meta-Analysis. *American Naturalist* 180: 70- 82.
84. Royer DL, Peppe DJ, Wheeler EA, Niinemets U (2012) Roles of climate and functional traits in controlling toothed vs. untoothed leaf margins. *American Journal of Botany* 99: 915-922.
85. Rubio de Casas R, Kovach K, Dittmar E, Barua D, Barco B, et al. (2012) Seed afterripening and dormancy determine adult life history independently of germination timing. *New Phytologist* 194: 868-879.
86. Safran RJ, Flaxman SM, Kopp M, Irwin DE, Briggs D, et al. (2012) A robust new metric of phenotypic distance to estimate and compare multiple trait differences among populations. *Current Zoology* 58: 426-439.
87. Samuels J, Meachen J, Sakai S (2012) Postcranial morphology and the locomotor habits of living and extinct carnivorans. *Journal of Morphology* In press.
88. Santos JC (2012) Fast molecular evolution associated with high active metabolic rates in poison frogs. *Molecular Biology & Evolution* 29: 2001-2018.
89. Schmidt J, Piekarski N, Olsson L (2012) Cranial muscles in amphibians: development, novelties and the role of cranial neural crest cells. *Journal of Anatomy* doi: 10.1111/j.1469-7580.2012.01541.x.
90. Schrey A, Richards C (2012) Within-genotype epigenetic variation enables broad niche width in a flower living yeast. *Molecular Ecology*: 2559-2561.
91. Schrey A, Richards C, Meller V, Sollars V, Ruden D (2012) The role of epigenetics in evolution: the extended synthesis. *Genetics Research International*.
92. Servedio MR, Kopp M (2012) Sexual selection and magic traits in speciation with gene flow. *Current Zoology* 58: 510-516.
93. Slater GJ, Harmon LJ, Wegmann D, Joyce P, Revell LJ, et al. (2012) Fitting models of continuous trait evolution to incompletely sampled comparative data using approximate Bayesian computation. *Evolution* 66: 752-762.
94. Sliwa L, Miadlikowska J, Redelings BD, Molnar K, Lutzoni F (2012) Are widespread morphospecies from the *Lecanora dispersa* group (lichen-forming Ascomycota) monophyletic? *Bryologist* 115: 265-277.
95. Smith DM (2012) Exceptional Preservation of Insects in Lacustrine Environments. *PALAIOS* 27: 346-353.
96. Snell-Rood EC, Moczek AP (2012) Insulin signaling as a mechanism underlying developmental plasticity: the role of FOXO in a nutritional polyphenism. *PLoS ONE* 7: e34857.
97. Soltis P, Soltis D, editors (2012) *Polyploidy and Genome Evolution*. Heidelberg: Springer.

PUBLICATIONS FROM NESCENT SUPPORTED PROJECTS IN YEAR 8, CONTINUED

98. Stansbury M, Moczek A (2012) The evolvability of arthropods. In: Minelli A, Boxshall G, Fusco G, editors. *Arthropod Structure and Development: Major Features and Evolutionary Patterns*. Berlin: Springer Verlag.
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113. Wei CA, Beardsley PM, Labov JB (2012) Evolution Education across the Life Sciences: Making Biology Education Make Sense. *Cbe-Life Sciences Education* 11: 10-16.
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APPENDIX H:

PRESS FROM NESCENT SUPPORTED PROJECTS IN YEAR 8

CATALYSIS MEETING

Peter Ungar
Jerome Rose
John Sorrentino

2012. An evolutionary theory of dentistry. *Science Magazine*.

GRADUATE FELLOW

Paul Durst

2012. Huge hamsters and pint-sized porcupines thrive on islands. *EurekaAlert*.

Paul Durst

2012. How island isolation evolves giant rodents. *Futurity*.

JOURNALIST IN RESIDENCE

Michael Martin

2012. Allergies as a blessing in disguise. *New York Times*.

Michael Martin

2012. The mysterious case of the vanishing genius. *Psychology Today*.

LONG-TERM SABBATICAL

Dena Smith

2012. Ancient crickets hint at the origins of insect hearing. *EurekaAlert*.

Dena Smith

2012. 50-Million-year-old cricket and katydid fossils hint at the origins of insect hearing. *Science 360*, *NSF's Daily News Feed*.

Dena Smith

2012. Hear that? Insects can, and it's the sound of a hunting bat. *MSNBC*.

Dena Smith

2012. 50-million-year-old crickets with ears. *Futurity*.

Christina M. Caruso

2012. Compromises between quantity and quality are common in animals, but do the same tradeoffs hold true for plants and their flowers? *EurekaAlert*.

Michael Wade

2012. Not all altruism is alike, says new study. *EurekaAlert*.

Michael Wade

2012. Not all altruism is alike. *Indiana University News Office*.

POST-DOCTORAL FELLOW

Julie A. Meachen

2012. Prehistoric predators with supersized teeth had beefier arm bones. *EurekaAlert*.

Julie A. Meachen

2012. Powerful arms saved saber-toothed killers' fearsome fangs, study shows. *History Channel*.

Julie A. Meachen

2012. Wrestling ninjas -- why sabre-toothed predators have massive arms. *Discover Magazine*.

Julie A. Meachen

2012. Turns out, sabertooths had arms like Popeye. *MSNBC*.

Julie A. Meachen

2012. Sabre-toothed cats had weaker teeth than today's house cats—and relied on strong forelimbs to subdue struggling prey. *Daily Mail*.

Julie A. Meachen

2012. Sabertooth predators packed a punch. *Nature*

Julie A. Meachen

2012. John Batchelor Podcasts. *WABC Radio New York*.

Samantha Price 2012. For most of human history, being an omnivore was no dilemma. *National Public Radio*.

Samantha Price 2012. Scientists trace evolutionary history of what mammals eat. *National Science Foundation*.

Samantha Price 2012. New study traces the evolutionary history of what mammals eat. *Eurekalert*.

Juan C. Santos 2012. Athletic frogs have faster-changing genomes. *Eurekalert*.

Juan C. Santos 2012. Fitness tests reveal frisky frogs have faster-changing genomes. *Wired Magazine*.

Clinton D. Francis 2012. Noise pollution is changing forests. *New York Times*.

Clinton D. Francis 2012. Not just for the birds: Man-made noise has ripple effects on plants, too. *Eurekalert*.

Clinton D. Francis 2012. Pipe down! That noise might affect your plants. *National Public Radio*.

Clinton D. Francis 2012. Man-made noise disrupts the growth of plants and trees. *BBC News*.

Clinton D. Francis 2012. All that human noise has an effect on nature, too. *MSNBC*.

Clinton D. Francis 2012. How industrial noise helps and hurts plants. *Scientific American*.

Clinton D. Francis 2012. Noise pollution affects plants, too. *Discovery News*.

Clinton D. Francis 2012. Man-made noise can affect plants, as well as animals. *Christian Science Monitor*.

Clinton D. Francis 2012. Industrial roar changes nearby plant reproduction. *Science News*.

Clinton D. Francis 2012. Study suggests manmade noise affects plant dispersal and flower pollination. *Audubon Magazine*.

Clinton D. Francis 2012. A song for all seasons: Scientists find birds that live in fluctuating weather are better singers. *Daily Mail*.

Carlos A. Botero 2012. Changes in weather add to birds' marital woes. *New York Times*.

Carlos A. Botero 2012. Why we cheat: Bird mating habits used to explain infidelity in new study. *Huffington Post*.

Carlos A. Botero 2012. Climate change increases mate-swapping in birds. *Scientific American*.

Carlos A. Botero 2012. In shifty climates, birds sleep around. *Discovery News*.

Carlos A. Botero 2012. In uncertain climates, birds will sleep around. *MSNBC*.

Carlos A. Botero 2012. Unpredictable weather makes birds unfaithful. *The Globe and Mail*.

Julie A. Meachen 2012. Ice Age coyotes were supersized compared to coyotes today, fossil study reveals. *Eurekalert*.

Julie A. Meachen 2012. Coyotes were bigger before Ice Age, *Canis latrans orcutti* fossils show. *Huffington Post*.

Julie A. Meachen 2012. Honey, I shrunk the coyote. *Wired*.

Julie A. Meachen 2012. What caused big coyotes to shrink to modern-day size. *MSNBC*

Julie A. Meachen 2012. Why the coyote got small. *Science Now*.

Julie A. Meachen 2012. Coyotes shrank, wolves did not, after last ice age and megafaunal extinctions. *National Science Foundation*.

SHORT-TERM VISITOR

- Alan Bittles 2012. Why not marry your cousin? Millions do. *EurekaAlert*.
- Alan Bittles 2012. Cousin marriage health risks 'greatly exaggerated.' *The West Australian*.
- Alan Bittles 2012. End stigma of cousin marriage. *West Australia Today*.

WORKING GROUP

- Bruce Latimer 2012. The burdens of being a biped. *Science Magazine*.
- Linda Spurlock
- Rowan Lockwood 2012. Earth's Oceans 'Facing A Man-Made Major Extinction Event.' *Huffington Post*.
- Paul G. Harnik
- Seth Finnegan

APPENDIX I:

ACTIVE PROJECTS IN YEAR 8

NAME	INSTITUTION	PROJECT TITLE	START DATE	END DATE
CATALYSIS MEETING				
Andrew Groover Quentin Cronk	US Forest Service and University of California-Davis Department of Botany, University of British Columbia	Evolutionary Origins and Development of Woody Plants	5/1/2011	4/30/2012
David Liberles Sarah Teichmann	University of Wyoming Cambridge University	Modeling protein structural and energetic constraints on sequence evolution	5/1/2011	4/30/2012
Jason Wolf Hamish Spencer Francisco Ubeda	University of Bath University of Otago (New Zealand) University of Tennessee-Knoxville	An integrative understanding of the evolution of genomic imprinting	5/1/2011	4/30/2011
Jason Wolf Hamish Spencer Francisco Ubeda	University of Bath University of Otago (New Zealand) University of Tennessee-Knoxville	An integrative understanding of the evolution of genomic imprinting	5/1/2011	4/30/2011
Eric Crandall Cynthia Riginos	University of California-Santa Cruz University of Queensland	The Molecular Ecology and Evolution of the Indo-Pacific: A Collaborative Research Network	5/1/2011	4/30/2012
Peter Ungar John Sorrentino Jerome Rose	University of Arkansas John A. Sorrentino, DMD, FAGD University of Arkansas Main Campus (Fayetteville,AR)	Evolution of Human Teeth and Jaws: Implications for Dentistry and Orthodontics	10/25/2011	11/25/2012
John M Logsdon Lauri Lebo	University of Iowa Freelance	Evolution Outreach – Reporting Across the Culture Wars Engaging Media on Evolution	11/2/2011	12/3/2012
Alan Bergland Dimitri Petrov Paul Schmidt	Stanford University (CA) Stanford University University of Pennsylvania	Tracking the biotic response to global climate change through genomic analysis	11/2/2011	12/3/2012
Clifton Ragsdale Laure Bonnaud Leonid Moroz	University of Chicago University Paris Diderot-Paris 7 Whitney Laboratory for Marine Bioscience, Univ. of Florida	Paths to Cephalopod Genomics- Strategies, Choices, Organization	11/2/2011	12/3/2012
Michele Dudash Nat Holland	University of Maryland-College Park University of Houston	Transitions between Mutualism & Parasitism: Integrating Theory & Empiricism	11/2/2011	12/3/2012
Nina G Jablonski Mark Shriver Henry Gates	NESCent Pennsylvania State University Harvard University	Using Genetics and Genealogy to Teach Evolution and Human Diversity	1/3/2012	12/31/2013
Michael Travisano Matthew Herron William Ratcliff	University of Minnesota-Twin Cities University of British Columbia University of Minnesota-Twin Cities	Evolutionary Origins of Multicellularity	4/4/2012	3/31/2013
James Moody	Duke	Ecological Models and Social Networks: How evolutionary forces shape networks and communities	4/9/2012	3/31/2013
John Parker Edward Hackett	NCEAS Arizona State University	Advancing Theory and Research on Scientific Synthesis	4/13/2012	3/31/2013
Paul Baker Christopher Dick Sherilyn Fritz	Duke University University of Michigan University of Nebraska-Lincoln	The Role of Mountains, Climate, and Landscape in Generating Amazon/Andean Biodiversity	4/23/2012	3/31/2013
Louise S. Mead Judi Brown Clarke Joseph L. Graves Jr.	BEACON Center for the Study of Evolution in Action BEACON Center for the Study of Evolution in Action North Carolina A&T State Univ.	K-12 Evolution Education and the Underserved	6/18/2012	10/01/2013

Name	Institution	Project Title	Start Date	End Date
GRADUATE FELLOW				
Elizabeth Scordato	University of Chicago	The role of divergence in multiple sexually selected traits in speciation by sexual selection	3/11/2012	3/31/2012
Kristin Lamm	North Carolina State University	A quantitative way to identify ancestors in the fossil record	8/23/2012	12/7/2012
Matt Pennell	University of Idaho	Angiosperm Evolution and Diversification Within Adaptive Zones	8/9/2012	12/17/2012
Daniel Griffith	Wake Forest University (Winston-Salem, NC)	Origins of the C4 grassland system: phylogenetic biome assembly	1/18/2012	3/25/2012
Anna Hiatt	Oklahoma State University	Evaluation of the Validity and Reliability of the Evo Devo Concept Inventory	1/23/2012	5/11/2012
JOURNALIST IN RESIDENCE				
Ilan Greenberg	freelance (New York)	The science and surveillance of zoonotic diseases	9/8/2011	12/30/2011
Aaron Dubrow	Texas Advanced Computing Center	Following the Sequence	6/1/2012	7/1/2012
LONG-TERM SABBATICAL				
Dena Smith	University of Colorado	Evolution of the Coleoptera: A Paleontological Perspective	7/1/2011	6/30/2012
Michael Wade	Indiana University (Bloomington, IN)	A Critical Synthesis of Indirect Genetic Effects in Adaptive Evolution	9/1/2011	6/30/2012
Christina M. Caruso	University of Guelph (Canada)	The evolutionary ecology of genetic conflicts in plants	9/1/2011	5/31/2012
James S. Chisholm	University of Western Australia	Emotion and the Evolution of Culture	1/1/2012	12/31/2012
Martin Burd	Monash University (Australia)	Sexual dimorphism and sexual allocation in flowering plants: a synthesis of data	9/1/2012	8/31/2013
POSTDOCTORAL FELLOW				
Carlos A. Botero	NESCent	Evolution of conventional signals: from individuals to populations and back	1/1/2009	12/31/2011
Julie A. Meachen	NESCent	Competition, guild structure and evolution in the carnivora	8/1/2009	7/31/2012
Benjamin D. Redelings	NESCent	Improved probabilistic models of insertion/deletion for phylogenetic inference	9/1/2009	8/31/2012
Juan C. Santos	NESCent	Multivariate evolutionary analysis: integrating structural equation modeling and phylogenetics	10/1/2009	9/30/2012
Peter J. Unmack	NESCent	A gis based approach to a priori prediction in aquatic biogeography	8/1/2009	7/31/2012
Jenny L. McGuire	NESCent	Examining paleontological extinction patterns to predict modern extinction vulnerability	9/1/2010	1/31/2012
Jennifer Verdolin	NESCent	Integrating behavioral syndromes into social networks: optimal distribution of phenotypes and group stability	9/1/2010	8/31/2012
Clinton D. Francis	NESCent	Acoustic signal space conservatism: a framework for signal flexibility in noise	1/1/2011	1/1/2013

Name	Institution	Project Title	Start Date	End Date
POSTDOCTORAL FELLOW (CONTINUED)				
Rafael F. Rubio de Casas	NESCent	Dispersal evolution in the angiosperms: the origin of heterocarpy	5/1/2010	4/30/2012
Elizabeth J. Sbrocco	NESCent	Exploring environmental correlates of range limits across a marine biodiversity hotspot	1/1/2012	12/31/2013
N. Adam Smith	NESCent	Evaluating effects of temporal distribution of fossil calibrations on divergence analyses	11/1/2011	10/31/2013
Paul G. Harnik	NESCent	Ecological controls on evolutionary rates in marine systems	9/1/2011	8/31/2013
Kate Hertweck	NESCent	Comparative biology of transposable element proliferation	9/1/2011	8/31/2013
Mira Han	NESCent	Gene evolution in genomic context: Integrating genomic location into gene evolution models	9/1/2011	8/31/2013
Tami Cruickshank	NESCent	Population genetics of maternal effects and their influence on molecular evolution	9/1/2011	8/31/2013
Joshua Martin	NESCent	Quantitative Predictions of RNA Evolution	7/2/2012	11/30/2014
SHORT-TERM VISITOR				
Rebecca Safran	University of Colorado	An Integrative Evolutionary Approach to Examine Sexual Selection as a Mechanism of Speciation	3/18/2012	3/28/2012
Hafiz Maherali	University of Guelph (Canada)	Influence of photosynthetic capacity on the evolution of plant fungal interactions.	9/15/2011	12/15/2011
Courtney Murren	College of Charleston	Reaction Norm Evolution	10/10/2011	12/2/2011
Else Fjerdingstad	Last Queens College CUNY, currently none	What shapes the global patterns of mating strategies in social insects?	10/18/2011	1/17/2012
Scott Miller	University of Montana-Missoula	Evolutionary trade-offs in natural versus engineered enzymes	3/10/2012	5/15/2012
Alan Bittles	Murdoch University	The mating structure of early human populations, and its genetic consequences	3/30/2012	4/28/2012
Rubén Torices	Universidade de Coimbra	The evolution of dispersal syndromes: a case study with the tribe Cichorieae (Asteraceae)	1/21/2012	3/2/2012
Robert Lanfear	Australian National University	Synthesizing methods and data to understand the mutational processes that shape genomes	6/15/2012	9/30/2013
Iliana Medina Guzman	Universidad de los Andes (Colombia)	Does environmental tolerance favor signal variability in calls of songbirds?	1/10/2012	3/20/2012
Corey Hart	Drexel University College of Medicine	Seeing is believing: Creating 3D environments to facilitate evolutionary education	1/30/2012	2/20/2012
Lila Fishman	University of Montana	Genetic conflict and plant evolution	3/10/2012	5/15/2012
Aaron W. Hunter Dave Pawson Ronald Clouse Gene Hunt	PETRONAS University of Technology, National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Institution, Washington DC American Museum Natural History National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Institution, Washington DC	The evolutionary development of species gradient and hybridization in indo-pacific deep water crinoid populations	6/18/2012	1/31/2012
Jonathan D. Marcot	University of Illinois	Paleontological and phylogenetic approaches to the study of diversification and extinction	6/18/2012	6/30/2012
Willem Hordijk	Smart AnalytiX	Evolution and Excess Complexity	9/30/2012	10/27/2012
Patricia Cabezas	Brigham Young University	The anomuran morphospace: testing alternative evolutionary pathways and diversification patterns in a highly disparate clade	11/14/2012	12/14/2012
Lee Hsiang Low	University of Oslo	The effects of sampling on the inference of the timing of diversifications	11/14/2012	12/7/2012
Rachel Rodman	none	"Branches Springing from One Root": New Lectures in Evolution, Incorporating Themes from Shakespeare's Plays	9/17/2012	12/14/2012

Name	Institution	Project Title	Start Date	End Date
TRIANGLE SCHOLAR				
Tyler Curtain	University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill	Darwin and Nietzsche: evolutionary thought within literary theory	1/15/2012	5/15/2012
WORKING GROUP				
John Gowdy David Wilson	Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute Binghamton University	Integrating evolutionary theory with behavioral economics	5/1/2010	4/30/2012
Michael Gavin	Victoria University of Wellington	Modeling the diversification of human languages	10/10/2010	10/10/2012
Paul G. Harnik Rowan Lockwood Seth Finnegan	Stanford University College of William and Mary California Institute of Technology	Determinants of extinction in ancient and modern seas	10/10/2010	10/10/2010
Dustin Rubenstein Nancy Solomon Steve Phelps Eileen Lacey	Columbia University Miami University University of Texas, Arlington University of California, Berkeley	Integrative models of vertebrate sociality: evolution, mechanism and emergent properties	10/10/2010	10/10/2010
Rebecca Price Kathryn Perez	University of Washington-Bothell University of Washington at LaCross	Evoci toolkit: concept inventories to assess conceptual understanding of evolution	10/10/2010	10/10/2010
Daniel Ksepka James Parham	North Carolina State University Alabama Museum of Natural History, University of Alabama	Synthesizing and databasing fossil calibrations: divergence dating and beyond	10/10/2010	10/10/2010
Colin P. Osborne Christopher Still Caroline A. E. Stromberg	University of Sheffield University of California-Santa Barbara University of Washington	Origins of c4 grasslands: a new synthesis of phylogeny, ecology, and paleobiology	10/10/2010	10/10/2010
David Wilson	Binghamton University	Evolutionary mismatch and what to do about it	10/10/2010	10/10/2010
William Cornwell Amy Zane Stephen Smith	UC Berkeley University of Missouri-St. Louis Brown University	Tempo and mode of plant trait evolution: synthesizing data from extant and extinct taxa	12/1/2010	12/1/2012
Jennifer Fewell James H. Hunt Dustin Rubenstein	Arizona State University North Carolina State University Columbia University	Large-scale demographic, network and behavioral trait analyses of sociality	5/1/2011	4/30/2013
Doris Bachtrog Catherine Peichel Judith Mank	University of California, Berkeley Fred Hutchinson Cancer Research Center University of Oxford	The tree of sex—a comprehensive synthesis of sex determination systems in eukaryotes	5/1/2011	4/30/2013
Arlin Stoltzfus Enrico Pontelli Rutger Vos	Center for Advanced Research in Biotechnology New Mexico State University University of Reading	HIP: Hackathons, Interoperability, Phylogenies	5/1/2011	4/30/2013
Jason Hoeksema	University of Mississippi	A working group to solve problems in model selection and phylogeny in mixed multi-factor meta analysis	11/2/2011	12/31/2013
Mark Schwartz Peter T. Ellison	New York University School of Medicine Harvard University	Infusing Medical Education with Evolutionary Thinking	11/4/2011	12/31/2013
Bruce Latimer Linda Spurlock	Case Western Reserve University Cleveland Museum of Natural History	The Perils of Being Bipedal: An Evolutionary Perspective on Human Musculoskeletal Disorders	11/4/2011	12/5/2013
Andrew MacColl Tim Coulson Stephanie Carlson Adam Siepielski	School of Biology Imperial College of London University of California-Berkeley University of San Diego	Environmental and demographic determinants of natural selection	3/5/2012	4/5/2013
Joshua Herbeck Viktor Müller Geoffrey Gottlieb Ruane Barnabas	University of Washington Eötvös Loránd University University of Washington University of Washington	The evolution of virulence in a human infectious disease: the case study of HIV	4/4/2012	5/5/2013
Margaret Yacobucci Pedro Marengo Dena Smith Roy Plotnick	Bowling Green State University Bryn Mawr College University of Colorado University of Illinois (Chicago)	Learning Evolution from the Fossil Record: K-12 Explorations in Deep Time	6/18/2012	7/19/2013

APPENDIX J:

PROJECTS SUPPORTED IN YEAR 8

CATALYSIS MEETING

James Moody	Ecological Models and Social Networks: How evolutionary forces shape networks and communities
Sherilyn Fritz Christopher Dick Paul Baker	The Role of Mountains, Climate, and Landscape in Generating Amazon/Andean Biodiversity
William Ratcliff Matthew Herron Michael Travisano	Evolutionary Origins of Multicellularity
Joseph L. Graves Jr. Judi Brown Clarke Louise S. Mead	K-12 Evolution Education and the Underserved

GRADUATE FELLOW

Matt Pennell	Angiosperm Evolution and Diversification Within Adaptive Zones
Philip Donoghue Daniel Ksepka James Parham Rachel Warnock	2012 sees the 50th birthday of the molecular clock, but has it reached maturity?
Pinar Yoldas	The Very Loud Orchestra of Endangered Species

JOURNALIST IN RESIDENCE

Aaron Dubrow	Following the Sequence
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LONG-TERM SABBATICAL

Martin Burd	Sexual dimorphism and sexual allocation in flowering plants: a synthesis of data
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POSTDOCTORAL FELLOW

Jeremy Van Cleave	Mechanistic trade-offs in evolution of microbial sociality, plasticity, and virulence
Joshua Martin	Quantitative Predictions of RNA Evolution
Courtney L. Fitzpatrick	Expanded Bateman Gradients: a synthetic refinement of sexual selection theory

SHORT-TERM VISITOR

Beaux Berkeley	Life history and environmental factors driving variation in mammalian sex allocation
Ronald Clouse Dave Pawson Gene Hunt Aaron W. Hunter	The evolutionary development of species gradient and hybridization in indo-pacific deep water crinoid populations

Roy Plotnick	Paleontology and Phylogeny of Insect Ears
Jonathan D. Marcot	Paleontological and phylogenetic approaches to the study of diversification and extinction
Lee Hsiang Liow	The effects of sampling on the interference of the timing of diversifications
Willem Hordijk	Evolution and Excess Complexity
Patricia Cabezas	The anomuran morphospace: testing alternative evolutionary pathways and diversification patterns in a highly disparate clade
Rachel Rodman	“Branches Springing From One Root”: New Lectures in Evolution, Incorporating Themes from Shakespeare’s Plays

WORKING GROUP

Stephanie Carlson Adam Siepielski Tim Coulson Andrew MacColl	Environmental and demographic determinants of natural selection
Geoffrey Gottlieb Viktor Müller Ruanne Barnabas Joshua Herbeck	The evolution of virulence in a human infectious disease: the case study of HIV
Dena Smith Pedro Marengo Roy Plotnick Margaret Yacobucci	Learning Evolution from the Fossil Record: K-12 Explorations in Deep Time